

**RELATIONSHIP OF OVERTHINKING WITH PROFESSIONAL LIFE
STRESS AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG PROFESSIONALS**

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Abstract

The current study examined the correlation of Overthinking with Professional life stress then Job Satisfaction amongst 300 professionals. Their age range was 22-48 years. Data was collected by using convenient sampling technique. Overthinking, Professional life stress and Job satisfaction were the study variables which were measured through Perseverative Thinking Questionnaire (PTQ Ehring et al., 2010), Professional life stress Scale (PLSS David Fontana 1989) and Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) by Weiss et al., 1967 respectively. Results supported all the hypotheses that are Overthinking positively correlated with Professional Life Stress, Overthinking and Professional Life stress are adversely associated with Job satisfaction. Results also exposed that there are no substantial changes between professional groups off these variables. All professional groups were high on their job satisfaction and lower on overthinking and professional life stress.

Keywords:

Job Satisfaction, Overthinking, Professional Life Stress, Professionals.

In today's organizations, the environment is becoming highly challenging and competitive for employees. With the passage of time, new technologies and skills are being discovered in the organization, and it is becoming more challenging for professionals to achieve organizational goals. The attainment of these goals requires skills and experience to compete at national and international levels. Professionals engage in overthinking both on positive and negative sides. On the positive side, they ruminate themselves to find an attainment of their organizational goals.

When overthinking on the negative side and engaging themselves in rumination, they find themselves unable to attain organizational goals. They experience professional stress and are less satisfied in their job. Although overthinking is not a medical term in and of itself, research shows that the tendency can be seriously harmful to our health. Overanalyzing often results in dwelling on the bad, going over the worst parts of the past, or worrying about the future (Hassan, 2019). Overanalyzing a single thought repeatedly to the point that it interferes with day-to-day functioning is known as overthinking. A person in the middle of an overthinking episode may find it difficult to take action, make decisions, or rid a particular thought from their mind.

First-level overthinking is a mild state that occasionally affects regular people, particularly during stressful situations. The second level of overthinking is a moderate level that is typical of anxiety disorder sufferers. People who overthink to a moderate degree are practical yet struggle to control their emotions and, as a result, have serious overthinking issues. These folks may experience issues like insomnia, excessive calorie or alcohol consumption, or smoking, and they are frequently more stressed than they should be. Mental constructs, which are obsessive ideas organized into a fabricated world, are related with the severe level of overthinking, which is the third level (Domina Petric, 2022).

Workplace stress or occupational stress is other terms for stress at work. These expressions, however, are used interchangeably to describe stress in the workplace. According to Hurrell et al. (1998), "a significant number of work-related environmental factors or particular occurrences thought to have an effect on the worker's health and wellbeing" are referred to as "professional life stressors." Numerous physical conditions and psychological issues, including chronic fatigue, sleeplessness, emotional disturbances, migraines, anxiety, melancholy, stomach ulcers, allergies, and other skin conditions, are caused by workplace stress. Heart attacks, accidents, and even suicides may be among the most severe effects (Di Martino 2003).

Organizations that are under work stress suffer losses as a result of employee unhappiness, negativity, high turnover rates, and absenteeism (Webster et al., 2010). Low levels of job satisfaction are correlated with high levels of work stress.

Theories of Professional life Stress According to transactional theory, stress results directly from a transaction between a person and their environment, which may tax their resources and endanger their welfare (Lazarus & Folkman, 1987).

The Person-Environment Fit theory one of the early interactional theories of job-related psychological discomfort, the fit hypothesis contends that stress at work results from a mismatch between an individual's skills, resources, and talents and the expectations of the workplace (Caplan, 1987; French et al., 1982).

